

EXPLORING PUPIL'S ACCEPTANCE AND SATISFACTION WITH VIDEO-BASED LEARNING MATERIAL

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Exploring Pupil's Acceptance and Satisfaction with Video-Based Learning Material

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Abstract

This study assessed the acceptance and satisfaction levels of Grade Six learners in Sierra Bullones District, Sierra Bullones, Bohol, during the School Year 2023-2024, focusing on video-based learning materials. The research aimed to craft an enhanced lesson guide based on the findings. Specifically, it aimed to evaluate the learners' acceptance of video-based materials and measure their satisfaction levels, while also exploring the correlations between perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, behavioral intention to use, actual usage, and satisfaction. The study employed a descriptive-correlational method, using a quantitative descriptive survey and an adapted questionnaire based on previous studies. Data were collected from Grade 6 learners across five elementary schools in Zone 2 of Sierra Bullones, Bohol, using a structured ten-day data-gathering process. Analysis included weighted mean calculations and Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation to interpret the findings. Results indicated high levels of acceptance and satisfaction among learners with video-based learning materials, underscoring their perceived usefulness and ease of use. Significant positive correlations were found between these factors and satisfaction, highlighting the materials' impact on learning outcomes. The study's findings support the Technological Acceptance Model, emphasizing the importance of designing and implementing effective instructional materials to enhance educational practices and learner satisfaction. Recommendations include continual improvement of materials, educator training, further research on acceptance factors, and exploration of instructional design elements to optimize learner learning experiences.

Keywords: *video-based instructional material, perceive ease of use, perceived usefulness, behavioral intention to use, actual usage*

Introduction

In recent years, the landscape of education has shifted significantly towards video-based learning materials, driven by the growing accessibility of digital platforms and learners' preferences for interactive and engaging content. This shift includes educational videos, tutorials, lectures, and multimedia presentations, allowing learners to engage with content at their own pace, thus enhancing comprehension and retention. According to Mayer (2017), multimedia learning, which integrates visual and auditory elements, improves learning outcomes by stimulating multiple sensory channels and facilitating deeper cognitive processing. As technology advances, video-based learning materials are set to play a crucial role in shaping the future of education, catering to diverse learning styles, and fostering a dynamic learning environment.

High-quality instructional materials are vital for effective teaching and learning, enhancing student engagement and information retention, and transforming the learning process into a compelling experience. The integration of technology in education has become indispensable, modernizing the learning environment and opening avenues for interactive and personalized learning experiences. Embracing technological advancements in instructional materials demonstrates the adaptability and innovation needed to meet contemporary educational challenges. Instructional materials enriched by technology bridge traditional pedagogical approaches with the modern, tech-driven educational landscape. Recognizing the transformative potential of these materials enables educators to foster an environment that supports effective learning and prepares students for the 21st-century knowledge economy.

Several studies have underscored the critical role of instructional materials in education. Osuala (2007) emphasizes that instructional resources are crucial for educators to structure and deliver education effectively, making challenging concepts easier to convey and enhancing students' academic performance. Borg (2011) asserts that science education cannot be effectively imparted without teaching equipment, highlighting the role of instructional materials in developing problem-solving skills and scientific attitudes. Ajayi and Ogunyemi (1990) underscore the importance of aligning instructional materials with the teaching process, ensuring students have access to necessary reference materials and can progress at individualized paces, leading to improved performance. Mishra (2001) identifies video as an effective medium for illustrating real-life activities, particularly beneficial for presenting hazardous and expensive experiments. Hampton (2002) emphasizes that video, by integrating auditory and visual elements, provides a multisensory experience that supports learners in mastering practical skills.

The utilization of video-based learning resources has gained prominence, offering dynamic and engaging content that meets contemporary learners' needs. Zhang, Zhou, Briggs, and Nunamaker (2006) highlight video's ability to present tangible objects and lifelike scenarios, though production can be cost-intensive. Tooth (2000) and Jung (2005) recognize the economic benefits of reusable video resources. Online videos reached almost 93% of internet users worldwide (Schepers, 2007). Studies show that short video clips enhance processing and memory recall, appealing to a wide audience and allowing natural information processing. Despite the benefits, online instructors must be mindful of potential issues with media delivery that can affect concentration, attention, interest, and

engagement.

The Department of Education (DepEd) recognizes the trend of video-based instructional materials, launching DepEd TV to convert self-learning modules into video lessons accessible through various platforms. According to a recent Kaltura survey, 75% of teaching staff report increased student interaction with course materials when video is used. However, educators often struggle to find current, legal, and engaging videos. Technology plays a crucial role in the field of education, particularly in the realm of teaching with video-based learning materials. As technology rapidly advances, the demand for skilled educators to effectively utilize and integrate these materials into their teaching strategies also increases (Parojenog, 2023).

Despite the growing body of research supporting the efficacy of video-based instructional materials, there is a lack of studies specifically examining their acceptance and satisfaction among primary school learners. This gap in the literature necessitates further investigation to understand the unique needs and perceptions of younger learners.

This study aims to assess the level of acceptance and satisfaction of video-based instructional materials among Grade Six learners in the Sierra Bullones District, Bohol. By evaluating learner perceptions, the research seeks to provide insights into the reception of video-based instructional resources within the educational framework. The findings aim to inform educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers about the effectiveness of integrating video-based materials in primary education, ultimately enhancing the quality of education in this specific academic domain.

Research Questions

This research assessed the level of acceptance and satisfaction of Grade Six learners in using learner's Video-Based Learning Materials in Sierra Bullones District, Sierra Bullones, Bohol during School Year, 2023-2024 as a basis for crafting an enhancement lesson guide. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of acceptance of video-based materials of the learners in terms of:
 - 1.1. perceived usefulness;
 - 1.2. perceived ease of use;
 - 1.3. behavioral intention to use; and
 - 1.4. actual usage
2. What is the level of satisfaction of video-based instructional materials for the learners?
 - 2.1. Is there a correlation between perceived usefulness and level of learners' satisfaction of Video-Based Instructional Learning Materials?
 - 2.2. Is there a correlation between perceived ease of use and level of learners' satisfaction of Video-Based Instructional Learning Materials?
 - 2.3. Is there a correlation between behavioral intention to use and level of learners' satisfaction of Video-Based Instructional Learning Materials?
 - 2.4. Is there a correlation between actual usage and level of learners' satisfaction of Video-Based Instructional Learning Materials?
3. Is there a significant relationship between learner's acceptance and satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials?
4. Based on findings, what enhance lesson guide can be presented?

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative approach, specifically utilizing a descriptive-correlational method. This methodology allows for the systematic examination of Grade Six learners' acceptance and satisfaction levels regarding video-based instructional materials. The research employs a validated questionnaire distributed among a stratified random sample from Sierra Bullones District, Bohol. Data analysis involves descriptive statistics to outline learner characteristics and correlational analysis to explore relationships between demographic variables and satisfaction levels. Ethical considerations ensure voluntary participation, confidentiality, and adherence to informed consent protocols.

Participants

The study included Grade 6 learners attending face-to-face classes at Zone 2 Elementary Schools in Sierra Bullones, Bohol. The entire student population from each school was selected for participation, comprising a total of 113 respondents distributed across San Juan Elementary School (30), Salvador Elementary School (37), Villa Garcia Elementary School (17), Magsaysay Elementary School (22), and Dusita Elementary School (7).

Instruments

The research employed an adapted questionnaire for its ease of administration, user-friendly nature, and quick scoring process, ensuring

efficient completion and assessment within a short timeframe for both respondents and researchers. This questionnaire comprised 20 items, specifically designed as the Learner Acceptance Scale and Learner Satisfaction Scale. Respondents rated their agreement or disagreement on a four-point Likert-type scale: strongly agree (4), agree (3), disagree (2), to strongly disagree (1). These items focused on perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, behavioral intention to use, and actual usage of video-based instructional materials, adapted from Rivera's (2022) study.

For assessing learner satisfaction with video-based instructional materials, seven items were used, covering overall satisfaction, material effectiveness, enjoyment during use, and likelihood of recommending the materials to peers. All items, except for overall satisfaction, were adapted from the Canarie Learning Program (2004) to ensure relevance and alignment with this study's specific context.

Procedure

The data gathering process for this study was meticulously planned and executed to assess students' acceptance and satisfaction with video-based learning materials. Beginning with formal approvals secured through a transmittal letter to the School Division Superintendent of Bohol Division, the research proceeded with clear instructions and systematic collection methods at five elementary schools. Over a ten-day period, questionnaires were distributed to and retrieved from 113 participating students. Following data collection, rigorous analysis was conducted to synthesize and interpret the findings, ensuring they provided valuable insights into the research questions.

Data Analysis

The analysis of data involved several statistical treatments. Responses regarding the acceptance and satisfaction of Grade 6 learners with video-based instructional materials were categorized into levels: Highly Accepting and Satisfied (4), Effective Acceptance and Satisfaction (3), Moderately Accepting and Satisfied (2), and Developing Acceptance (1). The weighted mean was calculated to determine the average response across questionnaire items, emphasizing varying levels of importance. Additionally, the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was employed to assess the correlation between learners' acceptance and satisfaction with these materials. The obtained correlation coefficient was compared against the table of significance values at the 0.05 level to ascertain statistical significance (Angeles, 2005: 269).

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without coercion. No harm happened to participants, and the study received ethics committee approval. The researcher declared no conflicts of interest and reported findings transparently and honestly. Cultural sensitivity was respected throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the learner's responses using Video-Based Learning Materials which were summarized using frequencies and percentages for categorical data and descriptive statistics (weighted mean and standard deviation) for quantitative data. The data includes the weighted mean, standard deviation, and a description for each item. The weighted mean represents the average score given by the respondents. The standard deviation values indicate the degree of variation or dispersion in the responses for each item.

Level Of Learner's Acceptance Of Video-Based Instructional Learning Materials

This exudes the Level of Learner's Acceptance of Video-Based Instructional Learning Materials in terms of Perceived Usefulness, perceived ease of use, behavioral intention to use, and actual usage.

Perceived Usefulness

The study assessed Grade 6 learners' acceptance of video-based instructional learning materials in terms of perceived usefulness. The overall weighted mean across items related to perceived usefulness was 3.52, indicating that learners highly accept and are satisfied with these materials. Specifically, learners found the materials to enhance their understanding of complex concepts ($M = 3.4336$, $SD = 0.8224$), effectively reinforce classroom learning ($M = 3.6194$, $SD = 0.6723$), make learning more engaging and enjoyable ($M = 3.7168$, $SD = 0.6743$), provide valuable supplements to traditional methods ($M = 3.3185$, $SD = 0.9089$), and help them retain and apply learned content effectively ($M = 3.5221$, $SD = 0.80286$). These findings align with previous research emphasizing the positive impact of video-based materials on student comprehension and engagement (Wang & Hsu, 2018; Chen et al., 2020).

Perceived Ease of Use

Regarding perceived ease of use, learners also showed high acceptance and satisfaction, with an overall weighted mean of 3.36. They reported finding it easy to navigate and access materials ($M = 3.5752$, $SD = 0.8107$), locate specific content ($M = 3.2389$, $SD = 0.8891$), use user-friendly interfaces ($M = 3.4690$, $SD = 0.8459$), adjust playback settings ($M = 3.0530$, $SD = 1.0423$), and follow clear instructions ($M = 3.4513$, $SD = 0.7675$). These results indicate that learners perceive video-based instructional materials as intuitive

and convenient, supporting their positive engagement with the learning content.

Behavioral Intention to Use

Grade 6 learners demonstrated a high level of acceptance and satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials in terms of their behavioral intention to use. The overall weighted mean across items ranged from 3.27 to 3.63, indicating strong inclinations among students ($M = 3.4903$, $SD = 0.8392$ overall). Specifically, they expressed a readiness to use these materials in future learning endeavors ($M = 3.4779$, $SD = 0.8874$), incorporate them regularly into study routines ($M = 3.5664$, $SD = 0.7545$), actively seek them out for self-improvement ($M = 3.6283$, $SD = 0.7928$), recommend them to peers ($M = 3.2743$, $SD = 0.8264$), and rely on them as valuable educational resources ($M = 3.5044$, $SD = 0.8977$). These findings underscore the significant motivational benefits associated with video-based materials (Giannakos et al., 2015).

Actual Usage

Grade 6 learners demonstrated a high level of acceptance and satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials in terms of their actual usage. The overall weighted mean across items ranged from 3.27 to 3.72, indicating strong engagement among students ($M = 3.4673$, $SD = 0.8407$ overall). Specifically, they actively used video-based instructional materials in their recent learning experiences ($M = 3.7168$, $SD = 0.6875$), incorporated them regularly into study routines ($M = 3.4513$, $SD = 0.8017$), considered them as primary resources for their learning needs ($M = 3.5398$, $SD = 0.7201$), frequently revisited and engaged with them for ongoing learning and skill improvement ($M = 3.2655$, $SD = 0.9821$), and relied on them as a substantial part of their educational journey ($M = 3.3628$, $SD = 0.9167$). These findings highlight the significant role of video-based materials in enhancing student engagement and educational outcomes. Students today are increasingly using educational videos for learning various skills and subjects. Research has shown that videos enhance processing efficiency and memory recall, catering to diverse learning preferences through visual and auditory modalities. June et al. (2014) found that YouTube videos fostered critical thinking skills among university students, enhancing engagement and participation in learning activities.

Level of Learners' Satisfaction of Video-Based Instructional Learning Materials

Grade 6 learners demonstrated a high level of acceptance and satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials in terms of their satisfaction. The overall weighted mean across items ranged from 3.35 to 3.57, indicating strong satisfaction among students ($M = 3.492$, $SD = 0.828$ overall). Specifically, learners expressed satisfaction with the overall quality of video-based instructional materials ($M = 3.558$, $SD = 0.767$), their ability to meet learning needs and expectations ($M = 3.566$, $SD = 0.742$), the variety and relevance of content offered ($M = 3.425$, $SD = 0.843$), the positive impact on learning outcomes ($M = 3.549$, $SD = 0.813$), accessibility and ease of use ($M = 3.522$, $SD = 0.757$), attention and interest held ($M = 3.354$, $SD = 0.925$), enhancement of understanding ($M = 3.531$, $SD = 0.825$), enjoyment ($M = 3.566$, $SD = 0.789$), and effectiveness in meeting learning objectives ($M = 3.487$, $SD = 0.867$). These findings underscore the significant role of video-based instructional materials in supporting positive learning experiences and outcomes.

The integration of videos into educational settings has been shown to enhance student satisfaction and engagement. For instance, Zhang et al. (2006) found that interactive video significantly improved learning outcomes and satisfaction among undergraduate students compared to non-interactive video and no video conditions. Similarly, Park and Cigas (2013) reported increased satisfaction levels and higher completion rates with the incorporation of video mini lectures in a computer science course, correlating with improved academic performance.

These studies highlight the multifaceted benefits of video-based instructional materials in fostering a conducive learning environment, enhancing student engagement, and improving academic outcomes.

Correlation between Perceived usefulness and Level of Learners' Satisfaction of Video-Based Instructional Learning Materials

The correlation between perceived usefulness and the level of learners' satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials examines the relationship between individuals' subjective evaluations of a technology's utility and their overall satisfaction with the learning resources. In the context of exploring learners' acceptance and satisfaction with video-based learning material, understanding this correlation is crucial as it elucidates how students' perceptions of usefulness influence their satisfaction levels, driving acceptance and engagement with such resources.

Based on the data, a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.59 indicates a moderately positive correlation between perceived usefulness and learners' satisfaction ($p = 0.000$). This significant relationship suggests that as perceived usefulness increases, learners' satisfaction with video-based instructional materials also tends to increase. This finding underscores the importance of designing materials perceived as valuable and relevant by learners, as it positively impacts their engagement and learning experiences. The correlation highlights the need for educators and designers to consider learners' perceptions of usefulness when developing and implementing video-based instructional materials, aiming to enhance satisfaction and ultimately improve learning outcomes.

Correlation between Perceived Ease of Use and Level of Learners' Satisfaction of Video-Based Instructional Learning Materials

The correlation between perceived ease of use and the level of learners' satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials

examines how individuals' perceptions of the usability of such materials impact their overall satisfaction. In the context of exploring learners' acceptance and satisfaction with video-based learning material, this correlation is essential as it sheds light on how students' ease of interaction with video-based resources influences their satisfaction levels, offering valuable insights into the factors driving acceptance and engagement with these instructional materials.

Based on the data, a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.61 indicates a moderately positive correlation between perceived ease of use and learners' satisfaction ($p = 0.000$). This significant relationship suggests that as perceived ease of use increases, learners' satisfaction with video-based instructional materials also tends to increase. The findings emphasize the importance of designing user-friendly video-based instructional materials that are easy to navigate, understand, and interact with. When materials are perceived as user-friendly, learners are more likely to engage effectively and have positive learning experiences.

This correlation underscores the need for educators and instructional designers to prioritize ease of use when developing and implementing video-based instructional materials, aiming to enhance satisfaction and improve overall learning outcomes.

Correlation between Actual Usage and Level of Learners' Satisfaction of Video-Based Instructional Learning Materials

The correlation between actual usage and the level of learners' satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials examines how the extent of students' engagement with these materials impacts their overall satisfaction. Based on the data provided, a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.70 indicates a moderately positive correlation between actual usage and learners' satisfaction ($p = 0.000$). This significant relationship suggests that as learners utilize video-based instructional materials more frequently or extensively, their satisfaction with these materials also tends to increase.

The findings highlight the importance of encouraging and promoting the utilization of video-based instructional learning materials within educational settings. When learners actively engage with and incorporate these materials into their learning processes, they are more likely to derive value and satisfaction from them. This correlation underscores the need for educators to foster environments that support the effective utilization of video-based materials, thereby enhancing learners' satisfaction and contributing to improved learning outcomes.

Correlation between Behavioral Intention of Use and Level of Learners' Satisfaction of Video-Based Instructional Learning Materials

The correlation between behavioral intention of use and the level of learners' satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials examines how students' willingness to engage with these materials influences their overall satisfaction. Based on the data provided, there is a significant and moderately positive correlation between behavioral intention of use and learners' satisfaction (Pearson correlation = 0.63, $p = 0.000$). This significant relationship suggests that as students' intention to use video-based instructional materials increases, their satisfaction with these materials also tends to increase.

The findings underscore the importance of aligning the design of video-based instructional materials with learners' intentions and preferences. When materials are perceived as meeting students' intended use and learning objectives, they are more likely to enhance satisfaction and positively impact overall learning experiences. Educators and instructional designers can leverage these insights to tailor video-based resources effectively, thereby fostering greater acceptance and engagement among learners.

Significant Relationship between Learner's Acceptance and Satisfaction with Video-Based Instructional Learning Materials

The significant relationship between learner's acceptance and satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials examines the strong connection between students' willingness to adopt such materials and their overall satisfaction with them. Based on the data provided, there is a significant and strong positive correlation between learner's acceptance and satisfaction (Pearson correlation = 0.73, $p = 0.000$). This indicates that as learner's acceptance of these materials increases, their satisfaction with them also tends to increase.

The findings underscore the importance of designing and implementing video-based instructional materials that are engaging, relevant, and aligned with learners' needs and expectations. When these factors are considered, learners are more likely to accept the materials and experience higher levels of satisfaction, ultimately enhancing their learning outcomes.

In summary, the significant relationship between learner's acceptance and satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials highlights the importance of creating engaging and relevant materials that align with learners' needs and expectations.

Regression Statistics

Multiple R: 0.6995

R Square: 0.4893

Adjusted R Square: 0.4847

Standard Error: 0.3398

Observations: 113

These statistics indicate a moderate to strong relationship between learner's acceptance and satisfaction with video-based instructional

learning materials, explaining approximately 48.93% of the variance in learner satisfaction scores.

Based on the results of the study, it was evident that learners showed a high level of acceptance and satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials. The weighted mean values fell within the highly accepting and satisfied range for all items, indicating that learners actively utilized these materials, integrated them into their study routines, and regarded them as primary resources for their learning needs. Moreover, the positive impact of video-based instructional materials on learners' learning outcomes was notable, contributing to an enhanced understanding of complex concepts.

Furthermore, the study revealed significant correlations between various factors and learners' satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials. Perceived usefulness and ease of use were found to be positively correlated with satisfaction, suggesting that when learners perceived the materials as useful and easy to navigate, their satisfaction levels increased accordingly. Additionally, actual usage of the materials was positively associated with satisfaction, indicating that the more frequently learners engaged with the materials, the higher their satisfaction levels tended to be. Moreover, there was a significant positive correlation between learners' acceptance of the materials and their satisfaction, highlighting the importance of acceptance in determining satisfaction levels. Finally, learners' behavioral intention to use the materials was positively linked to satisfaction, indicating that a stronger intention to use the materials was associated with higher satisfaction levels.

In summary, the findings underscored the positive impact of video-based instructional learning materials on learners' learning experiences. The high acceptance and satisfaction levels observed among learners, coupled with the significant correlations between acceptance, usage, perceived usefulness, and satisfaction, highlight the importance of integrating such materials effectively into educational practices to enhance overall learning outcomes.

Conclusions

This study explored learners' acceptance and satisfaction with video-based instructional learning materials, focusing on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use within the Technological Acceptance Model (TAM). The findings robustly support TAM, revealing a significant relationship between learners' acceptance of these materials and their perceptions of utility and ease of use. These results underscore the pivotal role of perceived usefulness and ease of use in shaping attitudes towards educational technology.

Furthermore, the positive correlation observed between acceptance and satisfaction underscores their interconnectedness within TAM. When learners perceive video-based materials as valuable and user-friendly, their satisfaction with the learning experience tends to increase. These insights highlight the importance of developing video-based instructional materials that are engaging, relevant, and responsive to learners' needs and expectations. By applying TAM principles, educators and designers can optimize these materials to enhance acceptance and satisfaction among students.

While providing valuable insights, the study acknowledges limitations such as sample size and participant demographics, which may constrain the generalizability of the findings. Future research could address these gaps by exploring similar factors across diverse learner populations and educational contexts, thereby validating and expanding upon current findings.

In conclusion, this study enriches our understanding of how educational technologies influence learner experiences and outcomes. By integrating TAM principles into instructional design practices, educators can effectively elevate the acceptance and satisfaction of video-based instructional materials, thereby fostering more supportive and effective learning environments.

References

- Ajayi, K., & Ogunyemi, B. (1990). The relationship between instructional resources and students academic performance in selected secondary schools in Ogun State. *Journal of Educational Advancement*, 25(2).
- Angeles, R. (2005). RFID technologies: Supply-chain applications and implementation issues. *Information systems management*, 22(1).
- Borg, S. (2011). The impact of in-service teacher education on language teachers' beliefs. *System*, 39(3), 370-380.
- Chen, C. M., Wang, Y. H., & Chen, S. Y. (2019). The effects of pedagogical design strategies on learners' perception of video-based learning materials. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 27(2), 273-287.
- Chen, C. M., Wang, Y. H., & Chen, S. Y. (2020). The effects of video-based learning on mathematics achievement and perceived learning engagement in a flipped classroom. *Computers & Education*, 144, 103705.
- Chen, C. M., & Huang, Y. M. (2019). Elementary school students' perceptions and attitude toward video-based instruction. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 27(5), 572-586.
- Ferguson, J. R. (2013). Imagined agency: technology, unpredictability, and ambiguity. *Contemporary Music Review*, 32(2-3), 135-149.
- Ghee, T. T., & Heng, L. T. (2008). Efficacy of multimedia teaching instruction in elementary Mandarin class. *Proceedings of the Third*

Centre for Language.

Giannakos M, Chorionopoulos K, Chrisochoides N (2015) Making sense of video analytics: Lessons learned from clickstream interactions, attitudes, and learning outcome in a video-assisted course. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 16(1), 260–283.

Giannakos, M. N. (2013). Exploring the video-based learning research: A review of the literature. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 44(6), E191-E195.

Hampton, C. (2002). Teaching practical skills. In A. K. Mishra & J. Bartram (Eds.), *Perspectives on distance education: Skills development through distance education* (pp. 83–91). Vancouver, Canada: Commonwealth of Learning.

Jung, I. (2005). Innovative and good practices of open and distance learning in Asia and the Pacific (A study commissioned by UNESCO, Bangkok). Retrieved from <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0015/001529/152961e.pdf>.

Lawrence Neuman, W. (2014). *Social research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches*.

Mayer, R. E. (2017). Using multimedia for e-learning. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 33(5), 403-423.

Mishra, S. (2001). *Designing online learning*. Vancouver, Canada: Commonwealth of Learning. Retrieved from http://www.col.org/SiteCollectionDocuments/KS2001-02_online.pdf.

Neuman, W. R. (2016). *The digital difference: Media technology and the theory of communication effects*. Harvard University Press.

Osuala, E. C. (2007). *Introduction to research methodology*. Onitsha: African – FEP Publishers.

Parojenog, R. C. *Modified Automated Grading Tool for Senior High School Advisers*.

Reiser, R. A. (2001). A history of instructional design and technology: Part II: A history of instructional design. *Educational technology research and development*, 49(2), 57-67.

Rivera, A. T. (2022). Assessment of Student's Acceptance and Satisfaction Using Video-Based Instruction in Teaching Science. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Applied and Basics Subjects*, 2(6), 1-8.

Schepers, J., & Wetzels, M. (2007). A meta-analysis of the technology acceptance model: Investigating subjective norm and moderation effects. *Information & management*, 44(1), 90-103.

Tooth, T. (2000). *The use of multimedia in distance education*. Vancouver, Canada: Commonwealth of Learning. Retrieved from <http://www.col.org/SiteCollectionDocuments/KS2000%20multimedia.pdf>.

Varnhagen, S., & Fuchs, A. (2004). *CANARIE E-learning Program. Final Report of the Evaluation Team: Education Evaluation Sub-Group*. Edmonton: University of Alberta. Retrieved from the Internet on October, 29, 2004.

Wang, C. Y., & Hsu, C. K. (2018). An empirical study on the influence of video-based learning on students' learning motivation and academic achievement. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 21(4), 223-236.

Zhang, D., Zhou, L., Briggs, R. O., & Nunamaker Jr, J. F. (2006). Instructional video in e-learning: Assessing the impact of interactive video on learning effectiveness. *Information & Management*, 43(1), 15-27.

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